

Special Relativity, Energy and Measurement Part II

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In special relativity (and Einstein's energy-mass equivalence $E=mc^2$) it seems energy is equivalent to inertial mass which transforms as the fourth component of the 4-vector (pc, mc^2) . For example, if two objects, separated by a distance, are attached by a spring which is compressed until the two touch and are then fastened, there is potential energy as well as rest mass energy. This potential energy is treated as mass and is fully inertial mass. In other words, $m_1c^2+m_2c^2+\text{spring potential energy}=\text{rest mass } mc^2$ which is the fourth component of a 4-vector. This is not surprising because one could give each mass a kinetic energy (part of mass energy) in order to compress the spring.

A similar consideration appears in electrostatics. One may add charge onto a conductor (or build a spherical charged object) by forcing charge on the objects, i.e. fighting the electric field. This leads to a self-energy, but also to an enhanced electric field because extra charge on conductor or spherical charge increases the electric field associated with the object. Thus, the picture is not the same as that of two masses attached by a spring. In other words, if one gave each charge a kinetic energy (related to mass energy) and this is converted into potential energy, there is a new electric field created in space, i.e. a change in the distribution of electrostatic potential energy in space.

To investigate the difference, one may note that charge does not change when seen from a constantly moving frame and that due to the electric field there exists an energy $q\phi$, where ϕ is the electrostatic potential created by a charge Q . Thus, there are two energies in the picture (not necessarily mutually exclusive), the self-energy in creating Q and potential energy of the E field of Q . This potential energy transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. It, however, is associated with the E field and it seems one cannot double count energy.

We suggest that $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ is associated with two kinds of energy, an inertial type of energy and a kind of electrostatic field potential energy. One cannot simply add the two because the "momentum" associated with Lorentz transformations differs. Rest mass converts directly to a $m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ momentum, while $(0, q\phi)$ transforms to an $(A \text{ vector}, q\phi)$ where A is the magnetic vector potential which is linked to a magnetic field. In other words, ϕ is linked to both energy $q\phi$ and a piece of force $-q \text{ grad } \phi$ and $\text{grad } \times A$ and $-dA/dt$ are also linked with force, (one being magnetic field and the other a piece of the electric field). Thus, field energy is different from inertial mass which may be associated with a center-of-mass point.

It is known that if one calculates $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ as seen from a frame moving with a constant $-v$, ϕ transfers to ϕ' and A' which yield in turn E' and B' . These lead to $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2}\mu_0 B \cdot B$ as energy density. Integrating over all space and taking the nonrelativistic limit yields: $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E c^2 + \frac{4}{3}(\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E) v^2$. In other words, one does not retrieve the usual $\frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ (where m_0 is rest mass). We argue that this is because $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ is not all rest mass, but also includes field energy which transforms differently under a Lorentz transformation.

Rest Mass (Inertial Mass)

Inertial mass is an idea which exists in Newtonian mechanics. It is considered to be equivalent to gravitational mass. Special relativity considers the Lorentz transformation: $(0, m_{cc})$ to (p, m_{cc}) where $m_{cc} = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$.

Thus, m_{cc} is mass energy in the rest frame and $m_{cc} / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ mass energy as seen in the moving frame. Next consider a rest frame in which a particle moves. It has mass energy $m_{cc} / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$. If one performs a nonrelativistic expansion, i.e. uses $v/c \ll 1$, then $m_{cc} / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \approx m_{cc} + .5mv^2/c^2$. Both terms are considered to be mass energy pieces. The Lorentz transformation is linear so sums of energy transform into sums.

If one considers a particle moving into a repulsive potential, it loses kinetic energy which becomes potential energy. This kinetic energy was originally part of rest mass and so the potential energy should also be part of mass energy as long as it does not represent any other form of energy as well.

Thus, if one takes two masses separated by a distance and joins them by a spring, compresses the spring so the two masses touch and fastens the two, there exists potential energy. This should be equivalent to rest mass so that $m_1 c^2 + m_2 c^2 + \text{spring potential energy}$ transforms as a total rest mass of the two particle spring system.

Charged Conductor or Charged Sphere

In the previous section it was argued that potential energy be treated as rest mass. This is a basic idea of special relativity that is well known. Even temperature energy might be considered as extra mass energy.

As a result, one may calculate potential energy associated with adding charge to a conductor or creating a sphere of charge of finite radius. The result (1) is well-known and is:

$$\text{Electrostatic potential energy} = .5 \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E \quad ((1))$$

At first one may consider this to be potential energy which should be added to the rest mass of the conductor or sphere. In such a case, this piece should Lorentz transform to:

$$.5 \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((2))$$

((2)), however, is not the correct result. This begs the question: Why not?

While one may consider a charge with kinetic energy losing this piece of mass energy when arriving at the surface of the conductor or sphere and then being fastened, this is not the only consequence. In particular, the electric field and corresponding electrostatic potential are changed. This change is linked to energy because the potential energy of a test charge q is:

$$\text{Potential energy} = q \phi \quad ((3))$$

Here phi is created by the charge Q. Thus, not only is there a self-energy linked with the creation of Q, but a potential energy in its field linked to phi as the fourth component of a 4-vector because q is the same as seen from a moving frame.

In other words, there are two energies, self-energy and electrostatic potential energy. The electrostatic potential energy is directly linked to the form phi. One might argue that the potential energy is equivalent to the lost kinetic energy and it is, but the form of phi still matters because it determines the value of r (the distance from the center of the sphere). In other words, phi determines where energy will be. The lost kinetic energy of a single charge q is mass energy and it is completely converted into potential energy when arriving at an r (not on the surface) which should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. This potential energy, however, is part of the field system of Q. (When one assembles charge on a conductor, it loses its kinetic energy, but its E field adds to that of the conductor system.)

One way to consider this is to note that when assembling a charge Q, each little q1 has a kinetic energy, but also an electric field (and magnetic) surrounding it, but the spatial distribution of these fields change when each q1 arrives at the conductor or sphere surface. A new overall field is created and this involves a redistribution of energy because:

For a single little charge q1, self-energy is $.5 \epsilon_0 E(q1) \cdot E(q1)$, but the new field energy is not a sum of these even though the E field is:

$E = \sum q_1 E(q_1)$, but self-energy is: $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ which is not $\sum \epsilon_0 E(q_1) \cdot E(q_1)$

This is already known because kinetic energy is also lost.

This kinetic energy, however, is equivalent to q phi which is the electrostatic potential multiplied by q. There is energy associated with the form phi regardless of the value of the charge q. The energy associated with phi should be a piece of:

$$.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \quad ((4))$$

We argue because the notion of a field is based on a test charge. A field still exists (and its force) whether or not a physical charge q is present (because test charges exist). As a result, ((4)) cannot simply be considered to be part of rest mass.

One might argue that whether it is part of rest mass or not, it should transform as the fourth-component of a 4-vector, but we argue that this is not the case due to the different natures of rest mass and electrostatic potential energy. The latter is directly linked to force.

In other words:

$$(0, m_0 c) \text{ Lorentz transforms to: } (pc, m_0 c^2) \quad ((5))$$

P is momentum and it is related to force through impulse, i.e. $\int \text{Force} dt$. ((6))

On the other hand,

$(0, q\phi)$ Lorentz transforms to $(qA', q\phi')$ ((7))

qA' must be like a momentum, but there is something else in this picture, because $-\text{grad } \phi$ is the E electric field in the rest frame. Thus, in the moving frame one should consider:

$-\text{grad}' \phi' = \text{a piece of electric field } E'$ ((8))

We argue that the fact that one considers ϕ' at one r' position versus another implies one also consider A' at one position and another as well, because the two are part of the same 4-vector. If one gradient or gradient-like operation represents a field (force) a second should be linked to force as well in some way. If one considers a charge along the y axis in the rest frame and the charge moves along x , then the force is in y direction also in the moving frame. A' depends on velocity and disappears if $v=0$. Given that A' is a vector, one may consider:

$\text{Grad} \cdot A'$ and $\text{Grad} \times A'$ or a 2 degree tensor ((9))

$-\text{grad } \phi$ yields a vector and so to treat grad with A on the same footing, one may choose $\text{grad} \times A'$. One requires a force along the y direction for v along x , and so v should appear in the result for a kind of force. This suggests $qv \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ or magnetic force. One may also create a vector using: dA'/dt partial and this becomes part of the electric field. These results may also be obtained directly from Maxwell's em equations.

The point is that ϕ transforms in a very different manner from rest mass, but is still associated with energy. As a result, the potential energy $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ does not simply contribute to rest mass, we argue, but also to a kind of field energy which must be considered whether or not a charge q exists in the field or not. These two kinds of energies transform differently. As a result, one does not a priori expect that;

$.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E \rightarrow \text{Lorentz transform} \rightarrow (.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E) / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ ((10))

One must consider the fact that $q\phi$ transforms as energy and that ϕ' and A' which result are directly related to E' and B' which are used to calculate:

$.5 \epsilon_0 E' \cdot E' + .5/\mu_0 B' \cdot B'$ which is the self-energy density as seen in the moving frame ((11))

Calculating E' and B' from a Lorentz transformation of $(0, q\phi)$ and using:

$E' = -\text{grad}' \phi' - dA'/dt'$ partial and $B' = -\text{grad}' \times A'$ ((12))

yields an expression which becomes, as shown in Part I, in the nonrelativistic limit $v/c \ll 1$

$4/3 (.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E) v^2$ ((13)) Here v =velocity

If $(.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E)$ transformed as rest mass one would expect $.5$ instead of $4/3$. $4/3$ is too large because it also includes field energy. Even in the rest frame, $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ does not simply represent rest mass, but is also linked with potential energy. Thus we argue that one cannot simply consider potential energy to be mass energy if it is also associated with the creation with another kind of energy linked to a force which is the case for an electrostatic charge.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that potential energy cannot always be fully associated with mass (inertial) energy. It is possible that it may be also associated with a different kind of energy, namely field potential energy linked to a force. This piece of field potential energy Lorentz transforms in a different manner from rest mass energy, i.e. $(0, q \phi) \rightarrow (qA'c, q\phi)$. $-\text{grad}' \phi'$ yields a piece of force (it is energy, but is also part of a field) and so the grad' or rather $\text{grad}'x$ of A' and even d/dt' are linked to forces as well. As a result, bringing charges onto a conductor or sphere represents the creation of potential energy, but some of this is associated with a force field (electric field for a system at rest). Not all of the potential energy should be inertial mass. Furthermore, mass energy usually adds linearly. If one brings in many little charges to create an overall Q , the electric field of each adds, but their self-energies do not. One must calculate self-energy using the full E which also contains the kinetic energy contributions.

Thus, one considers a Lorentz transformation on $(0, q \phi)$ to yield ϕ' and A' which are then used to calculate $E' = -\text{grad}' \phi' - d/dt' A'$ and $B' = \text{grad}' \times A'$. These in turn yield the electric and magnetic potential energy in the moving frame, but part of this is mass energy and the rest a kind of field potential energy. Thus, $.5 \epsilon_0 E' \cdot E' + .5/\mu_0 B' \cdot B'$ is not equal to $(.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E) (cc + .5 vv)$ in the nonrelativistic limit because $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ is not fully rest mass, it contains field energy associated with an electric force. In fact, in Part I, it is argued that instead of $.5vv$ one obtains $4/3 vv$ which is a large energy.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison-Wesely 1980)